

Low-cost platform for real time data acquisition and fractional control with application to a DC motor

Hemza Abdel Fettah Berkani^{1,2}, Bouziane Keziz², Mohamed Lashab¹, Abdelbaki Djouambi²,
Abdelfateh Kerrouche³

¹Laboratory of Electronics and New Technologies (LENT), Department of Electrical Engineering,
Faculty of Sciences and Applied Sciences, Larbi Ben M'hdi University, Oum El-Bouaghi, Algeria

²Laboratory of Electrical Engineering and Automatics (LGEA), Department of Electrical Engineering,
Faculty of Sciences and Applied Sciences, Larbi Ben M'hdi University, Oum El-Bouaghi, Algeria

³School of Computing, Engineering and Built Environment, Edinburgh Napier University, Edinburgh, United Kingdom

Article Info

Article history:

Received Oct 24, 2022

Revised May 2, 2023

Accepted May 16, 2023

Keywords:

Embedded system

Fractional control

Identification

Low-cost

Real time

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a low-cost experimental platform for real time data acquisition, identification and fractional order control of some low dynamic systems using Arduino-Simulink interface. As a demonstrative example, a DC motor is considered and modeled as a first order plus time delay plant (FOPTD) using data acquisition-based Arduino setup. Then, simple analytical rules are used to design a robust fractional order controller (FOC) which required a high-performance computing. Several validation tests have been carried out using Arduino-Simulink interface. The comparison between the theoretical simulation and the experimental tests confirms that the proposed interface can be used to support research and teaching of feedback control systems using experimental tests and low-cost laboratory kit.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Hemza Abdel Fettah Berkani

Laboratory of Electronics and New Technologies (LENT), Department of Electrical Engineering

Faculty of Sciences and Applied Sciences, Larbi Ben M'hdi University

N10, Oum El Bouaghi 04000, Algeria

Email: berkani.hemza@univ-oeb.dz

1. INTRODUCTION

Fractional controllers such as the widely used proportional integral derivative (PID) controllers are well-known for control and modelling in most industrial applications such as engineering, chemistry and mathematics due to their simplicity [1]–[5]. However, previous research has indicated that these controllers have limitations in performance, flexibility, and control quality [6], [7].

In recent years, the use of fractional calculus in control theory has led the development of more faster and powerful FOCs [8]–[10]. These controllers can offer many advantages such as greater flexibility and improved robustness compared to classical controllers [11]–[13]. Numerous robust control techniques have been devised, including the commande robuste d'ordre non entier (CRONE) controller as presented in [14], and the PI α D μ controller introduced by Birs *et al.* in [15]. These methods use non-integer integration and differentiation actions. These techniques can improve the performance of control systems in the presence of uncertainties or disturbances. Many researchers have already proposed various methods for PI α D μ control design and synthesis to achieve a better control performance and a higher tracking accuracy for control applications [16]–[20]. However, one of the main challenges associated with FOCs is their time-domain simulation. Therefore, algorithms and models expressed with analytical solutions are often more complex and time consuming [21]. In addition, several numerical approximation methods e.g., Grunwald-Letnikov

(GL) are commonly used for this type of simulation [15]. Recently, Djouambi *et al.* proposed faster and an efficient filter for simulating and identifying fractional operators compared to other existing methods [21]. Other difficulty facing FOCs is related to the implementation of these controllers which require high performance computing and complicated numerical calculations [21]–[23].

The MATLAB/Simulink software is widely used for implementing complex control systems [6]. Within the MATLAB suite, there are numerous toolboxes and functions already developed for data acquisition, identification, and control design. On the other hand, the Arduino-Simulink interface is an alternative low-cost interface used for real-time data acquisition and communication. Arduino is an open-source platform which includes all the necessary tools and libraries already available on its website (arduino.cc). The additional Arduino IO package needed to link both platforms (Simulink and Arduino) and can be downloaded from the MathWorks website's file exchange webpage. In this paper, a low-cost platform design using fractional speed control of a direct current (DC) motor is proposed for real-time data acquisition. This is fully motivated by the outstanding robustness and performance quality of FOCs and the challenges of high computing power required for real-time implementation.

2. APPROACH AND MODELLING

2.1. Basic concepts of fractional calculus

The most commonly used definition of fractional calculus is that provided by Riemann-Liouville as shown in (1) [24]:

$$D^{-\alpha}f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t - \tau)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau) d\tau \quad (1)$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the Gamma function and $D^{-\alpha}$ is the fractional integral of order α . Under zero initial conditions. So, Laplace transform of (1) is (2).

$$D^{-\alpha}f(t) = s^{-\alpha}F(s) \quad (2)$$

In an automatic control system, the generalized fractional order transfer function of a process model is given by (3):

$$\sum_{i=1}^N a_i D^{\alpha_i} y(t) = \sum_{j=1}^M b_j D^{\alpha_j} u(t) \quad (3)$$

where $D^{(\cdot)}$ is the fractional derivative operation, α_i, α_j, a_i and b_j are real numbers.

The Bode's ideal transfer function also known as the optimal loop can be expressed as a fractional integral of a certain type as given by (4) [24]:

$$L(s) = \left(\frac{\omega_\alpha}{s}\right)^\alpha, 1 < \alpha < 2 \quad (4)$$

the desired unity gain crossover frequency is represented as ω_α . The loop's Bode plot demonstrates a magnitude with a fixed slope of -20α dB/dec and a phase with a constant value of $-\alpha \pi/2$. The phase margin relies only on the fractional order α and can be expressed as $\varphi_m = \pi(1 - \alpha/2)$ which results in the robust control systems' iso-damping property.

2.2. Description of the experimental platform

The experimental platform proposed in this study as shown in Figure 1 consists of the following components: 1) a personal computer, 2) Arduino uno (Atmel board) utilized as a data acquisition system (DAQ) for sending and receiving data to and from the computer, performing tachometer calculations, and generating pulse width modulation (PWM) signals, 3) a full-bridge motor driver L298N utilized for the smooth operation of the DC motor, 4) a 12-volt DC motor utilized as the actuator, 5) a DC motor (generator) utilized as a tachometer for measuring rotational speed, 6) an encoder wheel, and 7) power supply. The input/output configuration of the Arduino is provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Arduino I/O configuration

Pin	Type	Description	Pin	Type	Description
2	Digital input	Incremental encoder	11	Digital output	PWM signal
5	Digital output	PWM signal	12	Digital output	Used for output relay
7	Digital output	Forward direction	A0	Analog input	Measured generator voltage
9	Digital output	Backward direction			

$$G(s) = \left(\frac{k_n}{\tau s + 1}\right) e^{-Ls} \tag{5}$$

To identify the parameters k_n , τ and L , the setup was excited by a pseudo random binary signal (PRBS) input signal. The following MATLAB command is used to generate the PRBS sequence: `idinput (1001,'PRBS', [0 1/1], [0 5])`; using the MATLAB ident ToolBox for identification, the transfer function of the setup's model (voltage-voltage) of "DC motor" was identified experimentally to a FOPTD as (6).

$$G(s) = \frac{V_{out}(s)}{V_{in}(s)} = \left(\frac{0.4540}{0.591s + 1}\right) e^{-0.132s} \tag{6}$$

As shown in Figure 3, the transfer function of the setup voltage-speed can be given by (7):

$$\frac{\omega(t)}{v_{in}(t)} = \left(\frac{0.4540/K_{gen}}{0.591s + 1}\right) e^{-0.132s} \tag{7}$$

where K_{gen} is the voltage/angular speed ratio, this constant was found to be $K_{gen} \cong 1/1000$. Then, the angular speed of the DC motor is obtained as the voltage of the generator multiplied by 1000. Figure 4, presents the response excited by a PRBS signal.

Figure 3. Simplified setup scheme

Figure 4. Excitation signal (PRBS) and measured speed response (identification data)

4. FRACTIONAL-ORDER CONTROLLER DESIGN

A basic analytical design approach relies on gain and phase margin specifications was used to design a robust fractional order speed controller for the aforementioned DC motor. The transfer function of the designed fractional controller is given by [25] and shown as (8).

$$C(s) = k_p \frac{(Ts + 1)}{s^\lambda} = k_p \left(\frac{1}{s^\lambda} + Ts^{1-\lambda}\right) \tag{8}$$

The controller depicted in (8) is, in fact, a modification of a fractional $PI^\lambda D^\mu$ controller. Where $\mu = 1-\lambda$. The technique presented in [25] was applied to adjust the values of k_p , T , and λ . To achieve specific gain and phase margins ($A_m=10$, $\varphi_m=55^\circ$) for the control loop specifications, the subsequent fractional order controller was designed as in (9):

$$C(s) = 3.5653 \left(\frac{0.591s+1}{s^{1.38}} \right) \quad (9)$$

to obtain a practical form of the fractional controller in (9), the approximation method [25] was applied to approximate the fractional integration operator into workable filters. A Simulink model of the fractional controller was developed, followed by a validation of its performance using pure software and hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) real-time simulations prior to implementation [25]–[27].

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, results from simulation and experimental experiments are presented in order to validate the performance (robustness) of the investigated system using the designed fractional order controller. There are two communication modes between the Arduino board and MATLAB/Simulink: online and offline. In an online mode, the Arduino board runs the IO “server” package while the Simulink model runs on the host computer. The package runs in the background, listening for MATLAB commands from the Simulink model and responding via the serial port if necessary. In an offline mode, the Simulink model is transformed into code that runs on the Arduino board independently of the host computer, allowing the board to be disconnected from it. Figure 5 shows the components used to set up the application platform while Figure 6 and Figure 7 show the Simulink model and simulation results of the feedback loop with the designed fractional controller, respectively.

Figure 5. The components of the proposed platform

5.1. Robustness to gain variation test

To assess the robustness of the control system, the nominal plant gain k_n was varied by $\pm 50\%$. The resulting step responses are illustrated in Figure 8 and Figure 9. As shown in Figures 8 and 9, the simulation results are in agreement with the experimental results, indicating a high degree of consistency and similarity between them. Also, the overshoots of the closed-loop step responses are almost constant for different nominal plant gain values k_n , indicating that the control system is damping. This implies that the closed-loop system can maintain stability and performance even under varying gain conditions.

5.2. Robustness to load disturbances test

To perform the load disturbance test, the plant was introduced with a change in electrical load during steady-state operation. Specifically, the electrical load was set with the following values of $RL = 55 \Omega$ at $t = 20$ seconds to induce a parameter variation. Then, the plant was set back to $RL = 0 \Omega$ at $t = 40$ seconds. The results of this test are presented in Figures 10, 11, and 12.

Figure 6. Simulink model of the proposed platform

Figure 7. Simulated vs experimental results of speed responses (with $T_s = 0.1$)

Figure 8. Robustness test for a gain variation (simulation results)

Figure 9. Robustness test for a gain variation (experimental results)

Figure 10. Robustness test to load disturbance of speed response

Figure 11. Control effort with load disturbance (experimental results)

Figure 12. Control error with load disturbance (experimental results)

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a low-cost platform containing the necessary tools to deal with real time data acquisition and control using Arduino board has been developed. Arduino is the DAQ between Simulink and an experimental setup. Important robustness tests have been carried out to validate the proposed system. The validation has been successfully achieved through the use of a DC motor control. Therefore, the proposed architecture can be applied to other plants of FOPTD model. The experimental tests seem to be in agreement with the simulation and confirms that the proposed Arduino-Simulink interface can be used to support similar research applications. Also, the versatility and low cost of this platform make it a great option for hobbyists,

students, and professionals alike, and it will be an excellent starting point for learning about control systems and automation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Our sincere appreciation goes to all the individuals who provided valuable contributions to this paper. Their insights and support played a significant role in the successful completion of this work.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. P. Borase, D. K. Maghade, S. Y. Sondkar, and S. N. Pawar, "A review of PID control, tuning methods and applications," *International Journal of Dynamics and Control*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 818–827, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s40435-020-00665-4.
- [2] A. Tepljakov *et al.*, "Towards Industrialization of FOPID Controllers: A Survey on Milestones of Fractional-Order Control and Pathways for Future Developments," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 21016–21042, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3055117.
- [3] P. Bertias, C. Psychalinos, A. S. Elwakil, and A. G. Radwan, "Log-domain implementation of fractional-order element emulators," *2019 42nd International Conference on Telecommunications and Signal Processing, TSP 2019*, pp. 106–109, 2019, doi: 10.1109/TSP.2019.8768875.
- [4] A. Charef and D. Idiou, "Design of analog variable fractional order differentiator and integrator," *Nonlinear Dynamics*, vol. 69, no. 4, pp. 1577–1588, 2012, doi: 10.1007/s11071-012-0370-x.
- [5] A. Charef, M. Charef, A. Djouambi, and A. Voda, "New perspectives of analog and digital simulations of fractional order systems," *Archives of Control Sciences*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 91–118, 2017, doi: 10.1515/acsc-2017-0006.
- [6] V. E. Tarasov, *Handbook of Fractional Calculus with Applications*. De Gruyter, 2019.
- [7] A. Tepljakov, E. Petlenkov, and J. Belikov, "FOMCON: a MATLAB Toolbox for Fractional-order System Identification and Control," *International Journal of Microelectronics and Computer Science*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 51–62, 2011.
- [8] B. H. Abdelfettah, L. Mohamed, and D. Abdelbaki, "Synergy between fractional order control and industry 4.0: A bibliometric analysis," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 204, pp. 803–810, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2022.08.097.
- [9] C. Copot, C. M. Ionescu, and C. I. Muresan, "Image-based and fractional-order control for mechatronic systems: Theory and applications with MATLAB®," *Advances in Industrial Control*, pp. 1–206, 2020.
- [10] A. Tepljakov, E. A. Gonzalez, E. Petlenkov, J. Belikov, C. A. Monje, and I. Petráš, "Incorporation of fractional-order dynamics into an existing PI/PID DC motor control loop," *ISA Transactions*, vol. 60, pp. 262–273, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.isatra.2015.11.012.
- [11] T. Seghiri, S. Ladaci, and S. Haddad, "Fractional order adaptive MRAC controller design for high-accuracy position control of an industrial robot arm," *International Journal of Advanced Mechatronic Systems*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 8, 2023, doi: 10.1504/ijamechs.2023.128155.
- [12] F. N. Deniz, A. Yüce, N. Tan, and D. P. Atherton, "Tuning of Fractional Order PID Controllers Based on Integral Performance Criteria Using Fourier Series Method," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 50, no. 1, pp. 8561–8566, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2017.08.1417.
- [13] Y. Zhang, P. Lin, and W. Sun, "Nonlinear Control and Circuit Implementation in Coupled Nonidentical Fractional-Order Chaotic Systems," *Fractal and Fractional*, vol. 6, no. 8, 2022, doi: 10.3390/fractalfract6080428.
- [14] L. Chen, N. Saikumar, and S. H. Hosseinnia, "Development of Robust Fractional-Order Reset Control," *IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 1404–1417, 2020, doi: 10.1109/TCST.2019.2913534.
- [15] I. Birs, C. Muresan, I. Nascu, and C. Ionescu, "A Survey of Recent Advances in Fractional Order Control for Time Delay Systems," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 30951–30965, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2902567.
- [16] M. D. K. Jagatheesan, P. Shah, and R. Sekhar, "Fractional Order $\text{PI}\lambda\text{D}\mu$ Controller for Microgrid Power System Using Cohort Intelligence Optimization," *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 2022, doi: 10.2139/ssrn.4271332.
- [17] L. Xiong, P. Li, M. Ma, Z. Wang, and J. Wang, "Output power quality enhancement of PMSG with fractional order sliding mode control," *International Journal of Electrical Power and Energy Systems*, vol. 115, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.ijepes.2019.105402.
- [18] B. Boudjehem, D. Boudjehem, and H. Tebbikh, "Analytical Design Method for Fractional Order Controller Using Fractional Reference Model," *New Trends in Nanotechnology and Fractional Calculus Applications*, pp. 295–303, 2010, doi: 10.1007/978-90-481-3293-5_25.
- [19] B. Bourouba, S. Ladaci, and H. Schulte, "Optimal design of fractional order $\text{PI}\lambda\text{D}\mu$ controller for an AVR system using Ant Lion Optimizer," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 52, no. 13, pp. 200–205, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2019.11.304.
- [20] A. Djari, "Optimal Projective Synchronization of Non-identical Fractional-Order Chaotic Systems with Uncertainties and Disturbances Using Fractional Sliding Mode Control with GA and PSO Algorithms," *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, vol. 45, no. 12, pp. 10147–10161, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s13369-020-04570-y.
- [21] A. Djouambi, A. Charef, and A. Voda, "Numerical simulation and identification of fractional systems using Digital Adjustable Fractional order integrator," *2013 European Control Conference, ECC 2013*, pp. 2615–2620, 2013, doi: 10.23919/ecc.2013.6669678.
- [22] E. Tlelo-Cuautle, A. Dalia Pano-Azucena, O. Guillén-Fernández, and A. Silva-Juárez, *Analog/Digital Implementation of Fractional Order Chaotic Circuits and Applications*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2020.
- [23] A. Tepljakov, E. Petlenkov, J. Belikov, and M. Halas, "Design and implementation of fractional-order PID controllers for a fluid tank system," *Proceedings of the American Control Conference*, pp. 1777–1782, 2013, doi: 10.1109/acc.2013.6580093.
- [24] D. Izci, S. Ekin, M. Kayri, and E. Eker, "A novel improved arithmetic optimization algorithm for optimal design of PID controlled and Bode's ideal transfer function based automobile cruise control system," *Evolving Systems*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 453–468, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s12530-021-09402-4.
- [25] A. Charef, H. H. Sun, Y. Y. Tsao, and B. Onaral, "Fractal system as represented by singularity function," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 37, no. 9, pp. 1465–1470, 1992, doi: 10.1109/9.159595.
- [26] B. Keziz, A. Djouambi, and S. Ladaci, "A new fractional order controller tuning method based on Bode's ideal transfer function," *International Journal of Dynamics and Control*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 932–942, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s40435-020-00608-z.
- [27] H. A. Berkani, A. Djouambi, M. Lasheb, and B. Keziz, "Simulink Blocks Implementation for Fractional Order Models Simulation based On DAFI Filter," *2022 19th IEEE International Multi-Conference on Systems, Signals and Devices, SSD 2022*, pp. 997–1002, 2022, doi: 10.1109/SSD54932.2022.9955756.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Hemza Abdel Fettah Berkani is currently a PhD student in electronics and embedded systems at Larbi Ben M'hdi University, Algeria. He is an active member of both the Laboratory of Electronics and New Technologies (LENT) and the Laboratory of Electrical Engineering and Automatics (LGEA). His research interests are focused on the areas of embedded systems, fractional control, control systems, robust control, electronics and real-time applications. He can be contacted at email: berkani.hemza@univ-oeb.dz.

Bouziane Keziz is a post-doctoral research associate at the Electrical & Electronic Engineering Department, Larbi Ben M'hdi University, Algeria. He is also a member of the Laboratory of Electrical Engineering and Automatics (LGEA). His research interests include control systems, robust control, modelling and identification, fractional order systems and fractional calculus. He can be contacted at email: bouziane.auto@gmail.com.

Mohamed Lashab is a Professor at the Electrical & Electronic Engineering Department, Larbi Ben M'hdi University, Algeria. He is a member of the Laboratory of Electronics and New Technologies (LENT). His research interests are focused on the areas of Antennas and Propagation, Electromagnetics, Microwave Filters, Microwave Technology, ADS, RF Technologies, Scattering, Method of Moments, Electromagnetics and Metamaterial. He can be contacted at email: lashabmoh@yahoo.fr.

Abdelbaki Djouambi is a Professor at the Electrical & Electronic Engineering Department, Larbi Ben M'hdi University, Algeria. He is a member of the Laboratory of Electrical Engineering and Automatics (LGEA). His research interests include control systems, robust control, modelling and identification, fractional order systems and fractional calculus. He can be contacted at email: djouambi_abdelbaki@yahoo.fr.

Abdelfateh Kerrouche is a Lecturer at Edinburgh Napier University. He boasts extensive research expertise spanning a diverse array of fields, including optical sensors, automation and applied microbiology. He has amassed a significant body of published works in various national and international peer-reviewed journals and have presented scientific papers at events around the globe. His areas of interest include pathogen detection, water sample preparation, sensors, aquaculture, the Internet of Things (IoT) and renewable energy. He can be contacted at email: A.kerrouche@napier.ac.uk.